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Linking Privacy Concerns with Resistance to Chatbots in the Banking Sector: Creepiness as a Mediator and Need for Human Interaction as a Moderator

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Abstract

Despite the Popularity of Artificial Intelligence, consumers resist using AI-based virtual agents. Only a few limited research studies have identified the reasons for users' negative experience with chatbots. The study's objective was to uncover the underlying factor of customer resistance towards the chatbots of the banking sector. The study employed the SOR framework due to its low application in determining the negative user experience in chatbot studies. The research model hypothesized the relationship between privacy concerns (stimulus), creepiness (organism), and resistance toward chatbots (response). The need for human interaction was taken as a moderator. Data were collected from chatbot users by using an online survey questionnaire. Data were analyzed by using covariance-based structural equation modeling. The results confirmed the positive relationship between privacy concerns and customers' resistance towards chatbots. The mediation effect of creepiness was also supported; however, the need for human interaction as a moderator was not accepted as hypothesized. The study findings offer valuable insights for marketers, practitioners, and policymakers.

Keywords: privacy concerns, creepiness, resistance and chatbots

Introduction

Technology integration in financial institutions is essential in a market that is becoming increasingly competitive and where client expectations are constantly rising (Fares et al., 2023). One of the most widely used AI applications transforming the interaction between banks and their customers are chatbots powered by artificial intelligence (AI) (Eren, 2021). Chatbots are becoming a more significant communication tool for banks, implying that creating high-quality intelligent agents requires considerable time, money, and effort. However, many essential problems still need to be addressed despite chatbots becoming increasingly common in the banking sector such as do consumers' reactions to developments in AI-powered chatbots align with what banks anticipate? Do consumers find their interactions with chatbots satisfactory? Do they respect the chatbots' proficiency when engaging with these artificially intelligent entities? (Mou et al., 2023). Many banks have recently added chatbots to their services, primarily for intuitive and speculative purposes, in response to the trend toward digitization and the increasing excitement surrounding AI technologies. Customers are less responsive to this (new) technology than

many academics and practitioners had anticipated, despite the apparent advantages of chatbots (Ben Mimoun et al., 2017; Longoni et al., 2019). According to Ben Mimoun et al. (2012), many chatbots have disappeared due to their inability to draw in enough clients and meet their expectations. Furthermore, the current research's primary emphasis on AI-chatbot advancements has been enhancing efficacy and engagement capabilities. However, the notable hindrance to broad acceptance lies in their incapacity to deliver top-notch customer care (Adam et al., 2021).

However, studies have also highlighted challenges in adopting chatbots, such as frequently falling short of users' expectations, which causes resistance and discontent (Froehlich, 2018). Despite their ubiquitous availability, studies in the US and Germany have shown that only 50% of individuals utilize AI personal agents, suggesting underlying resistance to AI-based technology (Beyto, 2020). Given the widespread accessibility of AI personal agents to almost every customer, it is puzzling why more than half of the population does not utilize them (Handrich, 2021). Though the positive outcomes of AI adoption are evident from the existing body of knowledge (Song et al., 2022), the available literature somehow neglects the challenges associated with AI-based chatbot adoption (Sajtos et al., 2024; Trincado-Munoz et al., 2024). This paradigm shift motivates the researcher to examine the negative aspects or dark side of AI (Ooi et al., 2024; Trincado-Munoz et al., 2024). Some recent research studies highlighted the factors contributing to resistance towards AI-based technology (Laato et al., 2022; Talwar et al., 2020). Nonetheless, current researchers call for further research to examine the negative impact of AI causing consumer resistance toward adoption (Longoni et al., 2019; Mou et al., 2023; Ooi et al., 2024).

Limited papers have identified various factors contributing to customer resistance to AI-backed technology, particularly chatbots. Among them, it was recognized that users' concerns about their privacy and the way their information is stored, used, and disclosed to third parties are the leading cause of the lower adoption of conversational agents (Bouhia et al., 2022a; Dev & Dev, 2023). Since information privacy and security have emerged as the primary consumer concerns regarding the internet, algorithms, and the digital market environment (Brill et al., 2022), privacy concerns are being given more attention by academic researchers, social critics, and regulators (Martin & Murphy, 2017). Privacy

concerns are also considered an obstacle to adopting AI-based technologies (Kronemann et al., 2023). Studies have investigated privacy issues with virtual agents and identified invasiveness and loss of control concerns among users (Lutz et al., 2019; Seymour et al., 2023). Various models have been used to discuss privacy behaviors, for example, the privacy cynicism or calculus model (Wang & Kim, 2019), the social contract model (Liao et al., 2019), and the social response theory (Hsieh & Lee, 2021). However, Further investigation is necessary due to the intricate nature of privacy-related behaviors stemming from cognitive and emotional responses. Previous study indicates that if the underlying algorithms are calibrated without regard for consumer psychology and social standards, customers may perceive IVAs as “creepy” (Parviainen & Søndergaard, 2020). The field of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) has a longstanding tradition of examining technologies that consumers find unsettling or eerie. The term "creepy" was employed in privacy research to characterize technologies seen as possibly intruding on users' privacy in the case of smart home devices (Pierce, 2019). Since chatbots come with various negative user experiences, human intervention is sometimes necessary for this technology to serve customers truly; in general, humans provide better customer service. Humans can manage events and subjects more effectively in complex settings than chatbots (Forbes, 2019).

This study, therefore, examines the effect of privacy concerns arising from using chatbots to elicit a feeling of creepiness, which may result in customer resistance to chatbots in the presence of need for human interaction as a moderator through a lens of the SOR framework.

Theoretical Background

Stimulus Organism Response (SOR) Framework

According to the SOR paradigm, individuals will respond to environmental circumstances and exhibit specific behaviors (Kamboj et al., 2018). Prior research has expanded the SOR framework to many domains, such as consumer behavior in the retail business (Wang & Kim, 2019) tourism industry (Kabadayi et al., 2023) and in measuring resistance (Trautwein & Lindenmeier, 2019). Stimulus (S-stimuli) is the ambient or atmospheric cues in the online platform or individuals' subjective perceptions, such as values and beliefs (Kini et al., 2024). Stimulus can influence consumers' cognition or emotions (O-organism),

therefore influencing their behavioral results (R-response) (Eroglu et al., 2003). Past studies have employed SOR mainly to examine consumers' acceptance of chatbots (Ittefaq et al., 2024; T. Zhang et al., 2022). However, in chatbot research, SOR is underexplored in measuring resistance behavior (Jan et al., 2023).

Hypothesis Development

The Relationship Between Privacy Concerns and Customer Resistance Towards Chatbots In The Banking Sector

Privacy concerns refer to “individuals' perceptions regarding the potential hazards and adverse outcomes that may arise from collecting and disclosing personal information” (Yun et al., 2019). Since successful electronic transactions in the financial sectors include exchanging personal and financial information, privacy issues have become unavoidable, particularly in light of recent data security breaches (Chin et al., 2022; Mogaji et al., 2021).

When people have these unfavorable feelings about privacy issues, it sets off a chain of events that makes the particular scenario involving the chatbot seem “creepy” (Rajaobelina et al., 2021). Customers' reluctance to embrace or use such technologies is subsequently fueled by this perceived creepiness, as explained by the Appraisal tendency framework and technology/privacy paradox (Mou & Meng, 2024). Therefore, the study proposes that privacy concerns stimulate discomfort, where consumers feel the loss of control and uncertainty of their data, which leads to resistance, hypothesized as:

H1: Consumer privacy concerns are positively associated with chatbot resistance of banking customers

The Relationship Between Privacy Concerns and The Creepiness Of Customers Towards Chatbots In The Banking Sector

Creepiness is an “emotional response to a sense of wrongness that is difficult to articulate clearly (Shklovski et al., 2014)”. The notion of creepiness can be comprehended within the privacy technology paradox, also known as privacy cynicism (Hoffmann et al., 2016). Consumers experience a sense of uncertainty and powerlessness when deciding how their private information is shared (De Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2024), which, in turn, may further reinforce the perception that intelligent technologies are unsettling or creepiness (Rajaobelina et al., 2021). Privacy is a critical factor for chatbot-based customer care within the banking industry (Bouhia et al., 2022b), and as privacy concerns rise, so

does creepiness (Rajaobelina et al., 2021). Therefore, we hypothesize for our study that:

H2: Privacy concerns are positively associated in eliciting creepiness among customers of the banking sector.

The Relationship Between Creepiness and Customer Resistance Toward Chatbots In The Banking Sector

Past studies have contended that perceptions of creepiness may lead individuals to oppose the adoption of smart home devices by eliciting inhibiting object-based attitudes (Cenfetelli & Schwarz, 2011). Individuals possess innate processes that function as creepiness detectors, allowing them to maintain a safe distance from those displaying unsettling or dubious characteristics (McAndrew & Koehnke, 2016). Expanding on this idea, we suggest that these creepiness detectors might also be at play when people are exposed to new technology, causing them to feel wary and keep their distance from these AI virtual agents. In other words, people may be reluctant to use AI due to the unsettling sensations they evoke. Therefore, we hypothesize the same effect for chatbots

H3: Creepiness is positively associated with chatbot resistance of banking customers

The Mediating Relationship of Creepiness Between Privacy Concerns and Customer Resistance to Chatbots In The Banking Sector

Prior studies have demonstrated that how people perceive something as creepy can positively affect their resistance to specific consumer behaviors by increasing their concern about their privacy (Mou & Meng, 2024). Considering these factors, such as skepticism towards privacy, the “privacy paradox,” and the unsettling nature of human-computer interaction, consumers experience emotional distress, anxiety, as well as a cognitive reaction to the discomfort stemming from fear of unknown. These reactions are linked to the impression of creepiness (Mou & Meng, 2024; Rajaobelina et al., 2021).

Past studies found a negative relationship between creepiness and loyalty in service technologies (Rajaobelina et al., 2021). Past researchers have exclaimed that feeling of creepiness or discomfort is disruptive in adopting new technology (Zhang et al., 2014). It creates resistive behavior in the case of intelligent virtual agents (Mou & Meng, 2024). Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H4: Creepiness mediates the relationship between privacy concerns and chatbot resistance among customers of the banking sector

The Moderating Effect of the Need for Human Interaction

The need for human interaction is defined as “the importance of human interaction to the customer in service encounter” (Dabholkar & Bagozzi, 2002). Past studies on psychology and communication literature indicate humans desire social interaction. Hence, interaction is pivotal in elucidating certain aspects of human behavior. A survey of insurance companies signifies the importance of genuine interaction with the actual human being, especially when dealing with clients who have suffered a significant loss, loss of family or property; users should anticipate receiving not only technical support but also active listening and empathy from the person they are interacting with which machine cannot provide (De Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023). Nevertheless, chatbots are incapable of offering emotional support or human warmth. Based on these, we hypothesize:

H5: The high/low NHI moderates the relationship between privacy concern and creepiness, strengthening/weakening it among baking sector customers.

Figure 1: The Hypothesized Model

Methodology

The research philosophy for this study is based on Positivism. Positivism pertains to the significance of “posited” or “given (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The positivist emphasizes a rigorous scientific empiricist approach followed by a testable hypothesis, and the cycle is completed by contributing back to theory (Park et al., 2020). Similarly, this study utilized a deductive methodology, which is well-suited for this study because it enables the systematic testing of hypotheses based on the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR)

framework. The S-O-R paradigm acknowledges that internal cognitive and emotional processes, organisms and external stimuli play a significant role in determining responses. Given the model's holistic viewpoint, it is appropriate to comprehend the negative side of AI eliciting negative emotions and posing resistance among the consumers of banking using chatbots. The survey approach is commonly employed in combination with a deductive research strategy (Saunders et al., 2018). In the recent past, various studies have employed deductive-based quantitative research in the context of chatbots in banking such as to measure attitudes (Turnadžić et al., 2024), to examine effect of chatbot characteristics on satisfaction and continuance intention (Le & Nguyen, 2024), and customers' adoption intention in the banking sector (Srivastava et al., 2024). However, the quantitative method study is still scarce in the literature (Anayat & Rasool, 2024). Therefore, our quantitative research will contribute to the empirical findings in literature towards the dark side of AI.

Sample, Methods, and Data Collection

Chatbots are among the most widely used AI applications, transforming the interaction between banks and their customers (Eren, 2021). For this reason, the data were collected from customers in the banking sector. The data were gathered only from individuals with bank accounts and previously used chatbots. Screening questions were used to ensure they fulfilled the criteria of the study such as, "Have you ever used chatbots?" "Are you a bank customer?" and "How frequently have you used chatbots in the last two years?". Only individuals who met these requirements were subsequently given access to the questionnaire, as the past studies says that despite the popularity of chatbots, consumer's adoption of this technology is considerably low (Griffith & Simonite, 2018). Therefore, respondents already familiar with this technology were included explicitly through purposive sampling. The study notably targeted literate people because chatbots are still in their infancy stage. This was crucial because chatbots usually operate in English language, and the selected sampling strategy ensured that the participants understood the language, the chatbot used and conversed with the technology. The questionnaire was designed through google forms, and the final sample consist of 280 respondents after data screening for outliers and missing data. Table 1 presents data on demographics, where most respondents belong to a young population, that is, between 18-29 (n=130), and respondents aged 30-39 (n=150) became the part of the study. Past studies also confirmed that people

who belong to Generation Y (those born after 1980) prefer screen-based interactions rather than seeking support through a call centre or in-person assistance (Trivedi, 2019), therefore, the sample was drawn from young people as they are more tech-savvy and understand the technology much then the older people. Regarding educational background, most of the samples had graduate degrees, justifying the sample is educated and could converse with this technology.

Table 1: Sample Characteristics (n=280)

	n	(%)
Gender		
Male	160	57.6
Female	120	42.3
Age		
18-29	130	46.2
30-39	150	53.5
Education		
Undergraduate	101	36.0
Graduate	179	63.9
Personal income		
Less than 100,000	120	42.3
100,000-300,000	110	39.2
300,000 or above	50	17.0

Measurement of Constructs

Scales created by other marketing academics were adapted and used for this study to optimize the measures' content validity. Privacy concerns were measured with a 4-item scale developed by Malhotra et al. (2004), previously used in the chatbot context by Rajaobelina et al. (2021). The sample item is “ When the chatbot asks me for personal information, I sometimes think twice before providing it.” Creepiness was measured with a 7-item scale developed by Langer and König (2018) and adapted in the context of chatbots, e.g., Rajaobelina et al. (2021). The sample item is “I had a queasy feeling when using a chatbot. “The need for human interaction was measured by a 4-item scale

developed by Dabholkar & Bagozzi (2022), previously adapted in the context of chatbot studies, e.g., Ashfaq et al. (2020). The sample item is “Human contact in providing services makes the process enjoyable for me.” Similarly, the resistance scale was measured with a 3-item (Kim & Kankanhalli, 2009; Lapointe & Rivard, 2005) previously adapted in the context of chatbot studies (e.g., Cheng, Bao, et al., 2022). The scale anchor ranged from 1=Strongly disagree to 5=Strongly agree for all constructs.

Results

Psychometric Properties of Scale

The study conducted a confirmatory factor analysis to determine the reliability and validity of the measures, and the indices demonstrated a favorable alignment with the data. The values of the measurement model are as under ($\chi^2=241.665(129)$, $p=0.000$; comparative fit index [CFI] = 0.983; tucker lewis index [TLI] = 0.98; non-normed fit index [NNFI] = 0.965; incremental fit index [IFI]= 0.983; standardized root mean square residual [SRMR]=0.0274, and root mean square error of approximation [RMSEA]=0.036. The alpha coefficients and composite reliability were computed to evaluate the model’s reliability. The values were above the cut-off value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2017). The factor loadings of the items were above the threshold of 0.7, and for the convergent validity AVE for all the constructs ranged between 0.532 to 0.793, above the threshold of 0.50 presented in Table 2 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Two methods were used to determine discriminant validity. First, the square root of each construct’s AVE was greater than its highest correlations with any other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), as shown in Table 3. Another method we used was HTMT ratio of correlations. All the HTMT values were below the cut-off value of 0.90, thus indicating discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015), as shown in Table 4.

Table 2: Reliability Measures of the Scale

Construct	Items	Factor loadings	Cronbach alpha	AVE	Composite reliability (CR)
Resistance to Chatbots	RC3	0.734	0.800	0.574	0.801
	RC2	0.798			
	RC1	0.739			
Privacy Concern	PC4	0.735	0.857	0.602	0.857
	PC3	0.763			

		PC2	0.824						
		PC1	0.779						
Creepiness		CR7	0.741	0.888	0.532	0.888			
		CR6	0.729						
		CR5	0.740						
		CR4	0.741						
		CR3	0.753						
		CR2	0.714						
		CR1	0.685						
Need for Human Interaction		NH4	0.877	0.938	0.793	0.939			
		NH3	0.912						
		NH2	0.904						
		NH1	0.867						

Table 3: Summary of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

;	Indicator	Skewness	Kurtosis	Mean	Std Dev	RC	PC	CR	NHI
Resistance to Chatbots	RC3	-0.352	0.114	3.710	0.670	0.758			
	RC2	-0.373	0.569						
	RC1	-0.208	0.120						
Privacy Concern	PC4	-0.820	1.095	4.008	0.663	0.585	0.776		
	PC3	-0.740	1.002						
	PC2	-0.533	0.548						
	PC1	-0.557	0.685						
Creepiness	CR7	-0.448	0.643	3.729	0.624	0.616	0.632	0.729	
	CR6	-0.251	0.064						
	CR5	-0.244	0.030						
	CR4	-0.125	-0.216						
	CR3	-0.207	0.109						
	CR2	-0.277	0.267						
	CR1	-0.201	0.087						
Need for Human Interaction	NH4	-0.036	-0.966	3.025	1.158	0.196	-0.029	0.045	0.891
	NH3	-0.017	-1.171						
	NH2	-0.031	-1.036						
	NH1	-0.046	-0.985						

Note: Abbreviations: CFA - Confirmatory Factor Analysis; SD - Standard Deviation
Square root of the AVE values on the diagonal in bold and off diagonal values are correlations between the constructs.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (HTMT criterion)

	CR	NHI	PC	RC
CR				
NH	0.045			
PC	0.633	0.028		
RC	0.616	0.195	0.585	

Structure Equation Model (Sem) Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The sufficiency of the structural model was then estimated ($\chi^2 = 267.97(130)$, $p=0.000$; CFI=0.98; NNFI=0.961; IFI=0.98; RMSEA=0.04; SRMR=0.0422; TLI=0.976). The values represent the model's fitness. The summary of the results are presented in Table 5. The results showed that privacy concerns ($\gamma = 0.417$, $p=0.002$) of the customers of the banking sector are significantly associated with resistance towards the chatbot; therefore, H1 is supported. Similarly, privacy concerns with the chatbot ($\gamma = 0.634$, $p=0.002$) significantly drove user creepiness perceptions, thus supporting H2. Furthermore, the creepiness ($\gamma = 0.319$, $p=0.002$) among users showed a significant relationship in posing resistance among users, thus supporting H3. Further, the indirect effect was significant ($\gamma = 0.27$, $p=0.001$) thus supporting H4. Finally, the interaction effect model was performed for H5. However, the interaction effect was insignificant ($\gamma = 0.04$, $p=0.456$); therefore, we say that H5 is not supported.

Table 5: Parameter estimates and summary of hypothesis testing statistics (standardized)

Association	Estimates (β)	P value	Result
Direct Effect			
PC -----> CR	0.634	0.002	Supported
PC -----> RC	0.417	0.002	Supported
CR -----> RC	0.319	0.002	Supported
Indirect Effect			
PC -----> CR -----> RC	0.27	0.001	Supported
Interaction Effect			

PC*NHI -----> CR 0.04 0.456 Not supported

Note: Abbreviations: PC, privacy concerns; CR, creepiness; RC, resistance to chatbots; NHI, Need for human interaction.

To better understand the nature of moderating effect, we visualized the interaction effect by plotting the relationship between privacy concerns and creepiness at different levels of need for human interaction (see fig-2).

Figure 2: Interaction Effect Model

Direct Effect ————> ; Moderating Effect - - - - ->

Discussion and Conclusion

Artificial intelligence (AI) significantly disrupts digital business by enabling the creation of intelligent services and advancing digital transformation (Cheng, Lin, et al., 2022). AI is a double-edged sword, functioning as both a boon and a bane (Ma et al., 2023). The objective of the study was to examine the underlying factors that cause resistance among the users to use the chatbots or preference for human interaction in the services, as the past literature says that human interaction fulfills the social inclusion of people while taking services (Ashfaq et al., 2020; Song et al., 2022). The results of this study indicate that privacy concern related to sharing personal information with AI chatbots in the banking sector significantly contributes to negative emotions such as discomfort or creepiness. These negative emotions in turn lead to a negative user experience resulting in resistance

to using AI chatbots. Our study did not, however, support the moderating effect of the need for human interaction, suggesting that personal preferences for human interaction had no discernible impact on the association between privacy concerns and unfavorable user experiences. This outcome contradicts the previous findings (e.g., Ashfaq et al., 2020; Pierce, 2019; Sheehan et al., 2020). However, the past literature says that, when interacting with chatbots, users who are less experienced with human-computer interaction, especially those unfamiliar with self-service technologies, may be less confident and more apprehensive than seasoned users. Instead of depending on self-service technologies or an AI-based system, these less seasoned customers could feel more at ease, self-assured, and motivated to engage with a human support agent (Mou et al., 2019). The sample of this study is comprised primarily of young people who are generally more comfortable with self-service technologies, which may explain the insignificant moderation effect.

Previous literature indicates that stakeholders are disinclined to support AI-based chatbots since AI enhances the capacity of technology proprietors to gather, evaluate, amalgamate, and regulate customer data (Mazurek & Małagocka, 2019). Therefore, The issue of privacy is receiving increased scrutiny from academic researchers, social critics, and regulators (Martin & Murphy, 2017) as the knowledge-based digital marketplace, information privacy and security have emerged as the foremost consumer concerns associated with the internet, algorithms, and data (Mazurek & Małagocka, 2019).

Theoretical and Managerial Implication

This study is essential to scholars and financial institutions as it offers multiple theoretical and managerial insights. Initially, opposition to chatbots, like any innovation, appears apparent, but empirical research on this topic is limited and virtually absent with banking chatbots, constraining our comprehension of this phenomenon (Chaouali et al., 2024). Secondly, the study employed the SOR framework, which, unlike contemporary theories on innovation resistance, offers a more comprehensive approach to understanding the reasons behind customer responses to innovative technologies (Hsiao & Tang, 2021; Upadhyay & Kamble, 2023). Thirdly, most previous studies relied on qualitative methodologies, resulting in interpretation biases and inconsistent findings. This study facilitates empirical validation of the model using an established scale for quantitative outcomes. Given the swift advancements in technologies and innovations within the self-

service banking sector, this study is of significant relevance to banks from a management perspective. Banks striving to enhance customer service and engagement should comprehend the factors contributing to resistance against chatbots and devise appropriate strategies to mitigate various hurdles.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

While the model in this study is interesting and new to researchers, future researchers can take other negative user experiences, such as withdrawal (R. W. Zhang et al., 2024). Similarly, different variables, such as chatbot intelligence and information cocoons, can be investigated to adequately uncover why customers resist chatbots (Liang et al., 2023). This study sampled users from the banking sector; future researchers may include other high-involvement industries, such as hospitals, or do a comparative analysis between two high-involvement sectors to examine potential differences in consumer responses. Furthermore, this study has analyzed Pakistan's interests, recognizing that AI has considerable progress to achieve in this context. In contrast, developed countries may yield different outcomes, as AI has already experienced significant expansion within their borders.

The sample of this study primarily represents the younger population. However, individuals aged 50 and above may exhibit different emotional responses. Future researchers could aim to include diverse age groups to gain a more comprehensive understanding of emotional variations across all age groups. Furthermore, the moderation effect of the need for human interaction is insignificant in the study, which requires further investigation, as previous researchers exclaim that users exhibit different personality traits when interacting with humans or AI devices (Mou & Xu, 2017). Future researchers can examine personality traits requiring human interaction while taking AI services.

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